

A novel accurate model for tracking irregular particles: Development, implementation, and impact on biomass combustors

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A novel particle-tracking model developed, solving both translation and rotation.
- Drag/lift/torque coefficients from particle-resolved DNS used for higher accuracy.
- The model successfully demonstrated in simulation of real biomass/gas co-firing.
- Unique insights into particle rotation revealed, largely improving CFD predictions.
- A powerful tool for gas–solid flow CFD, offering accuracy, robustness & efficiency.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Multiphase flows with irregular solid particles are ubiquitous in engineering applications, where particle rotation critically influences dynamics, mixing, phase interactions, and chemical reactions. Conventional particle-tracking models often neglect rotation, focusing solely on translational motion. Recent advances in drag, lift, and torque coefficients for irregular particles, derived from particle-resolved direct numerical simulations, underscore the need of models that account for both translational and rotational motion. This study bridges this gap by developing a novel model that accurately couples these motions. Leveraging drag, lift, and torque coefficients derived from thousands of particle-resolved simulations and an advanced analytical discretization scheme, this model ensures high accuracy, numerical robustness and broad applicability. The model’s capabilities are demonstrated through computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations of a natural gas/biomass co-fired burner, with biomass particles represented as prolate ellipsoids. The results reveal that biomass particles predominantly rotate around their minor axes, with rotation intensifying as particle size decreases. For equi-volume diameters decreasing from 16.5 mm to 165 μm, peak angular velocities around minor axes surge from approximately 4 to 6,600 rad/s, while those around major axes remain 1–2 orders of magnitude lower, rising from 0.03 to 71 rad/s. Compared to conventional models, this model provides unprecedented insights into particle rotation and significantly improves simulation outcomes without compromising computational efficiency. Notably, it extends particle residence times (~20 % longer in the 10-meter-long burner chamber), enhances mixing and lateral particle dispersion, and intensifies phase interactions, making it a valuable tool for simulating particle-laden multiphase flows in engineering applications.

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1. Introduction

Irregular solid particles are prevalent across numerous fields and applications, e.g., bioresources, chemical and energy systems, environmental processes, food and pharmaceuticals, thermal power generation, and energy storage. The rotation of irregularly shaped particles within multiphase flow systems or processes plays a critical role in particle dynamics, phase interactions, mixing efficiency, and chemical conversion, which are essential for the design and optimization of related industrial processes. Accurate modelling of these phenomena requires advanced simulation techniques that account for the effects of important forces and torques on irregular particles, as well as rotation-translation coupling (Michaelides, Crowe and Schwarzkopf, 2016; Voth and Soldati, 2017).

However, conventional models for tracking particles in dilute multiphase flows often simplify particles as equi-volume spheres and consider only translational motion driven by drag and gravity, as outlined in Eq. (1). These models typically employ spherical drag laws such as those proposed by Morsi and Alexander (1972), which depend solely on particle Reynolds number Re_p (Eq. (2)). As reviewed by Tabet and Gökalp (2015), this simplified approach is widely used in CFD simulation of reacting multiphase flows, such as biomass co-firing (e.g., Pérez-Jeldres et al., 2017) and tubular photobioreactors (e.g., del Olmo, Acién, and Fernández-Sevilla, 2022). Non-spherical drag laws, such as those developed by Haider and Levenspiel (1989) outlined in Eq. (3), which account for both particle Reynolds number and particle shape factors Θ , have also been widely applied, notably in CFD simulations of biomass co-firing to improve accuracy (Gubba et al., 2012; Karampinis et al., 2012; Bhuiyan and Naser, 2015; Milicevic et al., 2020; Knoll et al., 2021; and Milicevic et al., 2023). In Eqs. (1)–(3), ρ_p and ρ_f represent particle and fluid densities; V_p and d_p are particle volume and diameter; \vec{u} and \vec{v} are fluid and particle velocities; μ is fluid viscosity; and C_D is drag coefficient.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho_p V_p \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = \underbrace{\vec{F}_D}_{\text{drag}} + \underbrace{(\rho_p - \rho_f)V_p \vec{g}}_{\text{gravity}} \\ \text{where } \vec{F}_D = \rho_p V_p \frac{\vec{u} - \vec{v}}{\tau_r}, \tau_r = \frac{\rho_p d_p^2}{18\mu} \frac{24}{C_D Re_p}, Re_p \equiv \frac{\rho_f d_p |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|}{\mu} \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

$$C_D = a_1 + \frac{a_2}{Re_p} + \frac{a_3}{Re_p^2} \quad (a_i : \text{constants over several ranges of } Re_p) \quad (2)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} C_D = \frac{24}{Re_p} \left(1 + b_1 Re_p^{b_2} \right) + \frac{b_3 Re_p}{b_4 + Re_p} \\ \text{where } b_1 = \exp(2.3288 - 6.4581\Theta + 2.4486\Theta^2) \\ b_2 = 0.0964 + 0.5565\Theta \\ b_3 = \exp(4.905 - 13.8944\Theta + 18.4222\Theta^2 - 10.2599\Theta^3) \\ b_4 = \exp(1.4681 + 12.2584\Theta - 20.7322\Theta^2 + 15.8855\Theta^3) \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

Recently, significant advancements have been made in deriving accurate drag, lift, and torque coefficients for irregular particles using particle-resolved direct numerical simulations (PR-DNS). These coefficients provide a strong foundation for CFD modeling of industrial multiphase flows, where performing particle-resolved simulations is computationally prohibitive. Notable studies, such as those by Zastawny et al. (2012), van Wachem et al. (2015), Ouchene et al. (2016), Sanjeevi et al. (2018), Cao and Tafti (2018), Fröhlich et al. (2020), Sanjeevi et al. (2022), Wang et al. (2024a; b; c), have accurately quantified the drag, lift, and pitching torque on various irregular particles across a wide range of particle Reynolds number Re_p , aspect ratio β , and inclination angle ϕ_i . Using data-fitting techniques, these studies have derived reliable drag, lift and pitching torque coefficients (defined in Eq. (4),

facilitating more accurate CFD simulations in engineering applications.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} C_{D,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)} = \frac{|\vec{F}_D|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|^2 \frac{1}{4}\pi d_{eq}^2} \\ C_{L,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)} = \frac{|\vec{F}_L|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|^2 \frac{1}{4}\pi d_{eq}^2} \\ C_{T,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)} = \frac{|\vec{T}_p|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|^2 \frac{1}{8}\pi d_{eq}^3} \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

Here, $|\vec{F}_D|$, $|\vec{F}_L|$ and $|\vec{T}_p|$ are the magnitudes of the drag, lift and pitching torque, respectively; and d_{eq} is the diameter of an equi-volume spherical particle, $d_{eq} = \sqrt[3]{6V_p/\pi}$. For example, Wang et al. conducted a series of particle-resolved DNS to investigate drag, lift, and torque on large cylindrical particles. Initially, they examined the flow around a cylindrical particle with a fixed aspect ratio ($\beta = 9$) across a wide range of Reynolds numbers ($10 \leq Re_p \leq 2000$) and inclination angles ($0^\circ \leq \theta_i \leq 90^\circ$). Using traditional data fitting, they derived new models for drag, lift, and torque coefficients (C_D , C_L , and C_T) (Wang et al., 2024a). Next, they extended the study to cylindrical particles with varying aspect ratios ($6 \leq \beta \leq 22$), covering the same Reynolds number and inclination angle ranges. This systematic analysis led to new correlations for C_D , C_L , and C_T as functions of Re_p , θ_i , and β (Wang et al., 2024b). Finally, they expanded their work by also investigating heat transfer coefficients and using an N + 1 convolutional neural network (CNN) to improve data-fitting accuracy. The resulting correlations for drag, lift, torque, and average Nusselt number were derived with high precision across a broader parameter space: $1 \leq Re_p \leq 4000$, $0^\circ \leq \theta_i \leq 90^\circ$, and $1 \leq \beta \leq 30$ (Wang et al., 2024c). Fröhlich, Meinke and Schröder (2020) performed about 4,400 highly resolved simulations of flow around prolate ellipsoid particles across a wide range of flow and particle conditions ($1 \leq Re_p \leq 100$, $1 \leq \beta \leq 8$, $0^\circ \leq \phi_i \leq 90^\circ$), from which they derived new drag, lift, and pitching torque coefficients, $C_{D,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)}$, $C_{L,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)}$, and $C_{T,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)}$. Other representative sub-models for drag, lift and torque coefficients, recently derived from PR-DNS for non-spherical particles, are briefly summarized in Table 1. Detailed information on the model functions (e.g., $C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ}$, $C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ}$, $F(\beta)$, $G(\beta)$, $C_{L,mag}$, and $f_{L,shift}$) and model constants (e.g., a_i , b_i , c_i , and r_i) can be found in the corresponding references.

The resulting drag, lift, and pitching torque coefficients are both highly accurate and widely applicable to a broad range of flow and particle conditions. These breakthroughs underscore the need for a novel particle tracking framework that goes beyond conventional models by solving coupled translational and rotational motions while incorporating all key forces and torques accurately. This is particularly important because the new coefficients depend not only on particle shape and Reynolds number but also on particle orientation.

In the literature, several attempts have been made to develop closed particle-tracking models for biomass-firing simulations. For example, Yin et al. (2003) proposed a model for biomass suspension-firing simulation by solving coupled particle translation and rotation. However, their model relies on certain assumptions or approximations, such as the ‘‘cross flow principle’’ assumption in lift force calculations and an assumed distance between the center of pressure and the center of mass in pitching torque calculations. Bonafacic et al. (2015) developed a model for tracking cylindrical biomass particles in coal/biomass co-firing within a lab-scale entrained flow reactor. This model accounts for drag, gravity, pressure gradient, and lift forces, with drag and lift dependent on particle orientation. However, particle rotation was not solved but simplified using stochastic tracking instead. Guo et al. (2019) presented a spheroid model that solves both translational and rotational

motion, demonstrating its impact in simulations of pulverized biomass jet flows compared to conventional spherical particle models. However, the spheroid model did not account for lift force. Moreover, a common limitation of these models is their inability to properly incorporate the incidence angle into drag coefficients, regardless of the specific non-spherical drag laws employed. Very recently, Wang et al. (2025a) introduced a closed model and implemented it in a large-scale biomass co-fired boiler for virtual testing. However, its applicability is limited only to large biomass particles (millimeter-scale or larger) primarily due to numerical challenges.

This paper bridges critical gaps in the state-of-the-art literature by developing a novel and accurate particle-tracking model designed for irregular particles of all sizes in multiphase flows. The novelty of this model, compared to previous efforts, lies in the following key aspects. First, it resolves the coupled translation and rotation of particles by incorporating the non-spherical particle drag, lift, and pitching torque coefficients developed by Fröhlich et al. (2020). These coefficients are used for two main reasons: the authors provide the most comprehensive coefficient description, facilitating proper implementation; and the coefficients are based on approximately 4,400 highly resolved simulations conducted across a wide range of flow and particle conditions, enhancing their accuracy and applicability. Second, the model employs an advanced analytical discretization scheme to update particle velocities and orientations during time marching, eliminating numerical challenges and ensuring its applicability to particles of all sizes. Third, the model is demonstrated in an industrial biomass co-firing scenario, providing unprecedented insights into the rotational behavior of real biomass particles under actual firing conditions, encompassing particle sizes from a few hundred micrometers to tens of millimeters. Finally, the model maintains computational efficiency, delivering highly accurate, full-spectrum information on particle dynamics and conversion without

remarkably increasing the computational cost compared to conventional models. This ensures more reliable predictions of combustor performance while remaining practical for industrial applications.

2. The novel accurate model for tracking irregular particles

The new particle-tracking model solves the coupled translational and rotational motions of irregular particles. Translational motion, Eq. (5), is described in the inertial coordinate $\vec{x} = [x, y, z]$, while rotational motion, Eq. (6), is described in the particle coordinate system $\vec{x}' = [x', y', z']$, as shown in Fig. 1. $\vec{x}'' = [x'', y'', z'']$ represents the co-moving coordinate system, which originates at the particle frame's origin and has its axes aligned with the corresponding axes of the inertial frame.

$$\rho_p V_p \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = \underbrace{\vec{F}_D}_{\text{drag}} + \underbrace{\vec{F}_L}_{\text{lift}} + \underbrace{\vec{F}_{VM}}_{\text{virtual mass}} + \underbrace{\vec{F}_{PG}}_{\text{pressure grad.}} + \underbrace{(\rho_p - \rho_f) V_p \vec{g}}_{\text{gravity}} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{cases} I_x \frac{d\omega_x}{dt} - \omega_y \omega_z (I_y - I_z) = T_x \\ I_y \frac{d\omega_y}{dt} - \omega_z \omega_x (I_z - I_x) = T_y \\ I_z \frac{d\omega_z}{dt} - \omega_x \omega_y (I_x - I_y) = T_z \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here, ρ_p , V_p , \vec{v} , t , ρ_f , \vec{g} , \vec{F}_D , \vec{F}_L , \vec{F}_{VM} , \vec{F}_{PG} , $[I_x, I_y, I_z]$, $[\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z]$, and $[T_x, T_y, T_z]$ represent particle density, particle volume, particle velocity, time, fluid density, gravitational acceleration, drag force, lift force, virtual-mass force, pressure gradient force acting on the particle, moments of inertia about the three particle axes, particle angular velocities about the three particle axes, and the three torque components in the

Table 1
Representative drag, lift and torque coefficient sub-models derived from PR-DNS.

New correlations	Applicability	References
$C_D = C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ}) (\sin\phi_i)^{a_0}$	Prolate and oblate ellipsoids, discs, cylindrical fibers; $1 \leq Re_p \leq 300$; $Re_R = 0.1$ 1000; $\phi_i = 0$ 90°.	Zastawny, et al (2012);van Wachem, et al. (2015)
$C_L = \left(\frac{b_1}{Re_p^{b_2}} + \frac{b_3}{Re_p^{b_4}} \right) (\sin\phi_i)^{b_5+b_6 Re_p^{b_7}} (\cos\phi_i)^{b_8+b_9 Re_p^{b_{10}}}$		
$C_T = \left(\frac{c_1}{Re_p^{c_2}} + \frac{c_3}{Re_p^{c_4}} \right) (\sin\phi_i)^{c_5+c_6 Re_p^{c_7}} (\cos\phi_i)^{c_8+c_9 Re_p^{c_{10}}}$		
$C_R = r_1 (Re_R)^{r_2} + \frac{r_3}{(Re_R)^{r_4}}$ (counter – rotation torque coefficient)		
$C_D = C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ}) (\sin\phi_i)^2$	Prolate particles: $1 \leq \beta \leq 32$. C_D : $Re_p \leq 240$, $1 \leq \beta \leq 32$	Ouchene, et al. (2016)
$C_L = \left[F(\beta) Re_p^{0.25} + \frac{G(\beta)}{Re_p^{0.755}} \right] (\cos\phi_i) (\sin\phi_i)^{1.0028\beta}$	C_L : $1.21 \leq Re_p \leq 240$, $1 \leq \beta \leq 32$	
$C_{T1} = \ln(\beta) \left[\frac{F(\beta)}{Re_p^{0.18}} + \frac{G(\beta)}{Re_p^{0.51}} \right] (\cos\phi_i)^{0.9994\beta} (\sin\phi_i)$	C_{T1} : $1.21 \leq Re_p \leq 240$, $1 \leq \beta \leq 10$	
$C_{T2} = \left[\frac{F(\beta)}{Re_p^{0.3}} + \frac{G(\beta)}{Re_p^{0.9}} \right] (\cos\phi_i)^{0.9989\beta} (\sin\phi_i)$	C_{T2} : $1.21 \leq Re_p \leq 240$, $10 \leq \beta \leq 32$	
$C_D = C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ}) (\sin\phi_i)^2$	Prolate spheroid ($\beta = 2.5$), oblate spheroid ($\beta = 2.5$), spherocylinder ($\beta = 4$); $Re_p \leq 3000$; $\phi_i \leq 90^\circ$.	Sanjeevi, Kuipers & Padding (2018)
$C_L = \left(\frac{b_1}{Re_p} + \frac{b_2}{Re_p^{b_3}} + \frac{b_4}{Re_p^{b_5}} \right) (\sin\phi_i)^{1+b_6 Re_p^{b_7}} (\cos\phi_i)^{1+b_8 Re_p^{b_9}}$		
$C_T = \left(\frac{c_1}{Re_p^{c_2}} + \frac{c_3}{Re_p^{c_4}} \right) (\sin\phi_i)^{1+c_5 Re_p^{c_6}} (\cos\phi_i)^{1+c_7 Re_p^{c_8}}$		
$C_D = C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ}) (\sin\phi_i)^2 + 0.1280 Re_p^{0.2171} \sin\phi_i \cos\phi_i$	Cylinder ($\beta = 4$); $10 \leq Re_p \leq 300$; $0^\circ \leq \phi_i \leq 90^\circ$	Cao & Tafti (2018)
$C_L = \left(1.688 + \frac{6.617}{Re_p^{1.063}} \right) (\sin\phi_i)^{0.8222} (\cos\phi_i)^{0.9796}$		
$C_T = \left(19.28 - \frac{15.93}{Re_p^{-0.02476}} \right) (\sin\phi_i)^{0.8929} (\cos\phi_i)^{0.9769}$		
$C_D = C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ}) (\sin\phi_i)^2$	Prolate spheroids ($1 \leq \beta \leq 8$); $0.1 \leq Re_p \leq 2000$; $0^\circ \leq \phi_i \leq 90^\circ$.	Sanjeevi, Dietiker & Padding (2022)
$C_L = C_{L,max} \sin\left(90 \bullet \left(\frac{\phi_i}{90}\right)^{f_{L,shft}}\right) \cos\left(90 \bullet \left(\frac{\phi_i}{90}\right)^{f_{L,shft}}\right) (\phi_i \ln^\bullet)$		
$C_T = C_{T,max} \sin\left(90 \bullet \left(\frac{\phi_i}{90}\right)^{f_{L,shft}}\right) \cos\left(90 \bullet \left(\frac{\phi_i}{90}\right)^{f_{L,shft}}\right)$		

Fig. 1. (a) Inertial coordinate system $\vec{x} = [x, y, z]$ vs. particle coordinate system $\vec{x}' = [x', y', z']$, with the incidence angle (α_i) and inclination angle (ϕ_i) indicated. The inclination angle (ϕ_i) is commonly used in particle-resolved DNS; (b) Euler angles (θ, ϕ, ψ), where the line N denotes the intersection of the two planes.

particle coordinate system, respectively.

The drag, lift, virtual-mass, pressure gradient forces, and torque are calculated as follows.

$$\begin{cases} \vec{F}_D = \frac{1}{2} C_{D,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)} \rho_f \left(\frac{1}{4} \pi d_{eq}^2 \right) |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|^2 \vec{d}_D \\ \vec{F}_L = \frac{1}{2} C_{L,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)} \rho_f \left(\frac{1}{4} \pi d_{eq}^2 \right) |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|^2 \vec{d}_L \\ \vec{F}_{VM} = \frac{1}{2} \rho_f V_p \frac{d}{dt} (\vec{u} - \vec{v}) \\ \vec{F}_{PG} = \rho_f V_p \frac{D\vec{u}}{Dt} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{T} = & \underbrace{\mu \mathbf{K}_\omega \bullet (\vec{\omega}_f - \vec{\omega}_p)}_{\text{Viscous damping of vorticity of local fluid}} + \underbrace{\mu \mathbf{K}_s \bullet \vec{s}_f}_{\text{Flow-separation damping}} \\ & + \underbrace{\mathbf{A} \frac{1}{2} C_{T,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)} \rho_f \left(\frac{1}{8} \pi d_{eq}^3 \right) |\vec{u} - \vec{v}|^2 \vec{d}_T}_{\text{Pitching torque (nonsymmetric repartition of microscopic fluid velocity on particle surface)}} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where d_{eq} , μ , \vec{u} , and \vec{v} represent the particle equi-volume diameter, fluid viscosity, fluid velocity and particle velocity, respectively. The derivatives, $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{D}{Dt}$, used in the virtual-mass and pressure gradient forces, denote the time derivative following the moving particle and the fluid element, respectively, e.g., $\frac{du_i}{dt} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + v_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j}$ and $\frac{Du_i}{Dt} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j}$ (Maxey and Riley, 1983). The coefficients $C_{D,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)}$, $C_{L,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)}$, and $C_{T,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)}$ represent the drag, lift and torque coefficients, all of which depend on the particle Reynolds number (Re_p), aspect ratio (β), and inclination angle (ϕ_i). Similarly, \vec{d}_D , \vec{d}_L , and \vec{d}_T are the unit direction vectors for drag, lift and pitching torque, respectively. Additional variables include $\vec{\omega}_f$, the fluid angular velocity: $\vec{\omega}_p = (\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z)$, the particle angular

velocity; \vec{s}_f , the fluid strain rate; and \mathbf{K}_ω and \mathbf{K}_s , the diagonal resistance tensors for angular velocity and strain rate, respectively. The variables \vec{d}_D , \vec{d}_L , \vec{d}_T , $\vec{\omega}_f$, \vec{s}_f , \mathbf{K}_ω , and \mathbf{K}_s are calculated from their general definitions (Eqs. (9)–(11)). The drag, lift, and pitching torque coefficients $C_{D,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)}$, $C_{L,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)}$, and $C_{T,(Re_p, \beta, \phi_i)}$ are based on the work of Fröhlich et al. (2020), as detailed in Eqs. (12)–(14).

$$\begin{cases} \vec{d}_D \equiv \frac{(\vec{u} - \vec{v})}{|\vec{u} - \vec{v}|} \\ \vec{d}_T \equiv \frac{\vec{d}_D \times \vec{z}' \operatorname{sgn}(\vec{z}' \bullet \vec{d}_D)}{|\vec{d}_D \times \vec{z}' \operatorname{sgn}(\vec{z}' \bullet \vec{d}_D)|} \\ \vec{d}_L \equiv \vec{d}_D \times \vec{d}_T \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{cases} \vec{\omega}_f = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y'} - \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z'}, \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z'} - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x'}, \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x'} - \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y'} \right)^T \\ \vec{s}_f = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y'} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z'}, \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z'} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x'}, \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y'} \right)^T \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}_\omega = & \frac{16\pi\beta a^3}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a^2 + c^2}{a^2\alpha_0 + c^2\gamma_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a^2 + c^2}{a^2\alpha_0 + c^2\gamma_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\alpha_0} \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{K}_s = & \frac{16\pi\beta a^3}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a^2 + c^2}{a^2\alpha_0 + c^2\gamma_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a^2 + c^2}{a^2\alpha_0 + c^2\gamma_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

the particle coordinate system, as seen in Eq. (8).

$$\begin{cases} C_{D,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)} = C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ})(\sin\phi_i)^2 \\ \text{where } C_{D,\phi_i=0^\circ} = \underbrace{\frac{64\beta^{2/3}}{Re_p} \frac{1}{\chi_0/a^2 + \beta^2\gamma_0}}_{\text{Analytical } C_{D,Stokes,\phi_i=0^\circ}} \bullet \underbrace{\left(1 + 0.15Re_p^{0.687} + c_{d,1}(\log\beta)^{c_{d,2}} Re_p^{c_{d,3}+c_{d,4}\log\beta}\right)}_{\text{Correction function } f_{d,\phi_i=0^\circ}} \\ C_{D,\phi_i=90^\circ} = \underbrace{\frac{64\beta^{2/3}}{Re_p} \frac{1}{\chi_0/a^2 + \alpha_0}}_{\text{Analytical } C_{D,Stokes,\phi_i=90^\circ}} \bullet \underbrace{\left(1 + 0.15Re_p^{0.687} + c_{d,5}(\log\beta)^{c_{d,6}} Re_p^{c_{d,7}+c_{d,8}\log\beta}\right)}_{\text{Correction function } f_{d,\phi_i=90^\circ}} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{cases} C_{L,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)} = 2\sin(\psi_{\phi_i})\cos(\psi_{\phi_i})C_{L,max} \\ \text{where } \psi_{\phi_i} = \frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{\phi_i}{\pi/2}\right)^{f_{l,shift}}, \text{ in which } f_{l,shift} = \begin{cases} 1 + c_{l,1}(\log\beta)^{c_{l,2}} (\log Re_p)^{c_{l,3}} & \text{if } Re_p > 1 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ C_{L,max} = \underbrace{\left(1 + c_{l,4}Re_p^{c_{l,5}+c_{l,6}\log\beta}\right)}_{f_{l,max}} \bullet (C_{D,Stokes,\phi_i=90^\circ} - C_{D,Stokes,\phi_i=0^\circ})/2 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{cases} C_{T,(Re_p,\beta,\phi_i)} = 2\sin(\phi_i)\cos(\phi_i)C_{T,max} \\ \text{where } C_{T,max} = \frac{c_{t,1}(\log\beta)^{c_{t,2}}}{Re_p^{c_{t,3}}} + \frac{c_{t,4}(\log\beta)^{c_{t,5}}}{Re_p^{c_{t,6}+c_{t,7}\log\beta}} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In Eqs. (9)-(14), a and c denote the minor and major semi-axis of the particle, respectively. The constants $c_{d,i}$, $c_{l,i}$, $c_{t,i}$ ($i = 1, \dots, 8$) are derived from data-fitting based on the drag, lift and pitching torque results of thousands of highly resolved simulations, as tabulated by Fröhlich, Meinke and Schröder (2020). χ_0 , γ_0 , α_0 , and κ are the analytical shape coefficients for prolate ellipsoids with an aspect ratio $\beta = \frac{2c}{2a} > 1$, and can be calculated using Eq. (15).

$$\begin{cases} \chi_0 = \frac{-a^2\beta}{\sqrt{\beta^2-1}}\kappa \\ \alpha_0 = \frac{\beta^2}{\beta^2-1} + \frac{\beta}{2(\beta^2-1)^{3/2}}\kappa \\ \gamma_0 = \frac{2}{\beta^2-1} - \frac{\beta}{(\beta^2-1)^{3/2}}\kappa \end{cases} \quad \text{where } \kappa = \ln\left(\frac{\beta - \sqrt{\beta^2-1}}{\beta + \sqrt{\beta^2-1}}\right) \quad (15)$$

Since particle rotation is described in the particle coordinate system, the fluid angular velocity and fluid strain rate must be expressed in the particle coordinate system, as shown in Eq. (10). Similarly, a transformation matrix \mathbf{A} , Eq. (16), which describes the instantaneous orientation of the three particle axes in the inertial coordinate system, is used to transform the pitching torque from the inertial coordinate system to

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - 2(\varepsilon_2^2 + \varepsilon_3^2) & 2(\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3\eta) & 2(\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_3 - \varepsilon_2\eta) \\ 2(\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3\eta) & 1 - 2(\varepsilon_3^2 + \varepsilon_1^2) & 2(\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3 + \varepsilon_1\eta) \\ 2(\varepsilon_3\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2\eta) & 2(\varepsilon_3\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1\eta) & 1 - 2(\varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

in which the Euler parameters ($\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3, \varepsilon_4$) are calculated from the Euler angles (θ, ϕ, ψ) using Eq. (17) and are updated over time using Eq. (18).

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_1 = \cos\frac{\phi-\psi}{2}\sin\frac{\theta}{2} & \varepsilon_2 = \sin\frac{\phi-\psi}{2}\sin\frac{\theta}{2} \\ \varepsilon_3 = \sin\frac{\phi+\psi}{2}\cos\frac{\theta}{2} & \varepsilon_4 = \cos\frac{\phi+\psi}{2}\cos\frac{\theta}{2} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} d\varepsilon_1/dt \\ d\varepsilon_2/dt \\ d\varepsilon_3/dt \\ d\eta/dt \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \eta\omega_x - \varepsilon_3\omega_y + \varepsilon_2\omega_z \\ \varepsilon_3\omega_x + \eta\omega_y - \varepsilon_1\omega_z \\ -\varepsilon_2\omega_x + \varepsilon_1\omega_y + \eta\omega_z \\ -\varepsilon_1\omega_x - \varepsilon_2\omega_y - \varepsilon_3\omega_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Equations (5)-(18) present the mathematical formulation of the closed physical model. To make the model robust and applicable to irregular particles of all sizes, it is critical to adopt an appropriate numerical method for solving the ordinary differential equations (ODEs), such as those in Eqs. (5), (6) and (18). The explicit scheme is straightforward for updating particle velocities or Euler parameters at new time steps or locations. However, it could induce numerical challenges when applied to small irregular particles due to their very small moments of inertia. This limitation may confine the applicability of such a closed model to large particles, as encountered in previous attempts (Yin et al.

Table 2
The measured size distribution of straw particles fired in a utility boiler.

(1) Straw particles with nodes (solid pieces): density 250 kg/m ³									
Particle group #	0	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Long axis [mm]	130.3	90	70	50	32.5	18.5	9		
Short axis [mm]	4.8	4.1	4.7	5	4.3	3.7	3.8		
Mass fraction [wt%]	0.3784	0.5176	1.1923	2.7399	3.2728	2.4512	0.3690		
Equi-volume diameter, d_{eq} [mm]	16.5135	13.1412	13.2372	12.3311	9.6599	7.2425	5.7983		
Shape factor, Θ [-]	0.4281	0.4576	0.5153	0.5793	0.6263	0.6966	0.8117		
(2) Straw particles with heads (solid pieces, whisklike): density of 139 kg/m ³									
Particle group #	7	8	9	10	11	12			
Long axis [mm]	100.1	70	50	32.5	20	10.5			
Short axis [mm]	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5			
Mass fraction [wt%]	0.3562	0.2938	0.8011	1.0864	0.9617	0.6824			
Equi-volume diameter, d_{eq} [mm]	9.7904	8.6901	7.7681	6.7290	5.7236	4.6173			
Shape factor, Θ [-]	0.3783	0.4240	0.4710	0.5366	0.6155	0.7258			
(3) Regular straw pieces (with no node or head; hollow): density of 139 kg/m ³									
Particle group #	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Long axis [mm]	60	45	30	20	15	4.5	2.25	1.25	0.3
Short axis [mm]	2	1.95	1.73	1.49	1.42	0.53	0.33	0.22	0.1
Thickness [mm]	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.05
Mass fraction [wt%]	1.5588	4.0051	19.9105	22.9046	16.2812	11.6111	4.2174	2.3829	2.0256
Equi-volume diameter, d_{eq} [mm]	5.6836	5.1128	4.2584	3.4990	3.1155	1.0510	0.6772	0.4481	0.1651
Shape factor, Θ [-]	0.2648	0.2916	0.3396	0.3961	0.4351	0.4374	0.5754	0.6712	0.7788

Fig. 2. Suspension co-firing straw with natural gas in a 675 MW_{th} boiler: (a) Boiler; (2) Co-fired burner.

2004; Wang et al. 2025a). In contrast, this model employs an advanced analytical discretization scheme to update particle velocities and orientations at the new location ($n + 1$) based on the solutions at the previous location (n). For example, Eq. (19) illustrates a particle rotation equation along with the corresponding numerical solution for the particle rotation velocity at the new time or location, using the analytical discretization scheme.

$$\begin{cases} \text{ODE : } \frac{d\vec{\omega}_p}{dt} = \frac{1}{\tau_p} (\vec{b} - \vec{\omega}_p) + \vec{a} \\ \vec{\omega}_p^{(n+1)} = \vec{b}^{(n)} + e^{-\Delta t/\tau_p} \bullet (\vec{\omega}_p^{(n)} - \vec{b}^{(n)}) - \vec{a} \tau_p (e^{-\Delta t/\tau_p} - 1) \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

3. Implementation and impact of the novel model in biomass combustors

To demonstrate the implementation and impact of the novel particle-tracking model, a 675 MW_{th} natural gas/biomass co-fired boiler is selected, leveraging the wide particle size distribution of biomass particles co-fired in the boiler, as detailed in Table 2.

The particle size distribution was determined using 1.2 kg biomass sample, extracted just above the air lock and considered representative of the particles injected into the wall-fired furnace. It is worth noting that the biomass particles were produced by the first-generation preparation method (Yin, 2020), resulting in much larger particles than those typically used in modern suspension-firing boilers. The equi-volume particle diameter ranges from 16.5 mm to 165 μ m. Table 2 also

Table 3
Computational cases for implementation and impacts of the novel model.

CFD case	Biomass particle tracking model	Models in common
1	All the 22 groups of particles simplified as equi-volume spheres; only particle translation solved, using the spherical drag law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Eulerian framework for gas flow and Lagrangian discrete phase model (DPM) for particle phase, with interactive coupling between the two
2	All the 22 groups of particles simplified as equi-volume spheres; only particle translation solved, using the non-spherical drag law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realizable k-ε model for turbulence
3	All the 22 groups of particles modelled as prolate ellipsoids; the new, closed model used: solving both particle translation and rotation, incorporating drag/lift/torque coefficients derived from particle-resolved DNS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discrete model for thermal radiation: domain-based WSGGM for gaseous radiative properties Two-step global combustion mechanism for gas combustion with CO as the intermediate product Finite rate/eddy dissipation for turbulence-chemistry interaction Same particle surface area used in laws for particle-gas heat and mass exchange Single-rate model for biomass devolatilization Diffusion-limited char burning model due to large particle size, in which the same enhancement factor $\phi_{en} = (0.3\theta + 0.7)/\theta$ is used

Fig. 3. Grid independency study based on computational case 1.

provides the shape factor, Θ , defined as the ratio of the surface area of an equi-volume sphere to the actual surface area of an irregular biomass particle, which ranges from 0.2648 to 0.8117.

The 675 MW_{th} boiler features 18 natural gas burners arranged across three levels on the two side walls, as shown in Fig. 2(a). Of these, three burners were retrofitted for gas/biomass co-firing by removing the oil lance and flame scanner and clearing the center core for pneumatic transport of biomass particles. However, only one of the retrofitted burners, highlighted in Fig. 2(a), could co-fire biomass at any given time, resulting in relatively low overall biomass heat input in the boiler.

To better visualize the differences between the novel particle-tracking model and conventional models, CFD simulations are performed for one single co-fired burner chamber with a 10-meter axial length and a 3-meter inner diameter, in which the heat input from natural gas and biomass is approximately 50:50. The configuration of the 10-meter-long co-fired burner chamber is shown in Fig. 2(b), showing both side and inner views. The CFD simulations are conducted using Ansys Fluent 2023R2, with the novel particle-tracking model implemented via User-Defined Functions (UDFs).

Three computational cases are examined, differing only in the particle tracking model used, as summarized in Table 3. In Case 1 and Case 2, biomass particles are approximated as equi-volume spheres, while in Case 3, they are represented as prolate ellipsoids. Despite this difference, the effect of the non-sphericity of biomass particles on their

Fig. 4. Unprecedented insights into particle rotations of biomass particles of various particle sizes under real-world firing conditions.

thermochemical conversion, heat transfer, and mass transfer is fully accounted for in all three cases, in the precisely same way. Without this consideration, the outcomes would be much more distinctly different and fail to reveal the influence of the particle-tracking model alone. For the combustion of biomass volatiles, an “artificial” species, CH_{2.417}O_{1.172}, is employed to represent the volatile components. Both its composition and formation enthalpy are accurately determined from the proximate and ultimate analysis data of the biomass being co-fired. The oxidation of the volatile species is modelled using a two-step global

mechanism, with CO as the only intermediate product. Further details on the representation of biomass volatiles and the subsequent combustion modelling can be found in Yin et al. (2010). Apart from the common sub-models used in the three computational cases, the numerical solution methods remain identical for all cases. These include the SIMPLE algorithm for pressure–velocity coupling, unconditionally bounded upwind scheme for discretizing the convective terms in all the transport equations, a very low scaled residual of 10^{-8} for the continuity equation to assure calculations are not terminated prematurely while residuals continue to decrease, and 2000 iterations performed for each case starting from the same preliminary solution. The CFD solutions for all three cases are well converged, as evidenced by low residuals, relatively flat residual plots, stable temperature and oxygen values at a monitored location, and in particular very good overall heat and mass balance.

4. Results and discussion

Based on computational case 1, a grid-independent study was performed in a prior investigation of the 10-meter-long burner chamber using three different meshes (Yin et al., 2004). During the mesh generation, particular attention was paid to equi-angle skewness, growth ratio and aspect ratio of the cells to ensure a good mesh quality. For the grid-independence study, a refinement factor of about 1.5, defined as the ratio of the characteristic cell sizes, was used. Fig. 3 shows the gas temperature profiles along the burner chamber's center axis for the different meshes. The results indicate that further refinement beyond the intermediate mesh does not yield significant changes in the temperature profile. Given that the primary objective of this study is to demonstrate the efficacy of the novel model, the intermediate mesh is adopted in this work. This section presents and compares well-converged CFD results for the three computational cases, enabling a thorough evaluation of the influence of various models.

4.1. Groundbreaking insights into biomass particle rotations under real-world firing conditions

Although a few successful attempts have been made to implement closed particle-tracking models in biomass combustion simulations, as reviewed above, quantitative data on biomass particle rotations under actual firing conditions remain absent from the literature. This paper provides new insights into biomass particle rotations under real-world firing conditions. Fig. 4 illustrates the rotational behavior of biomass particles across five size groups as they travel through the 10-meter-long natural gas/biomass co-fired burner chamber. All these particle streams originate from the same location under identical conditions.

- Group 0: The largest particles, with a long axis of 130.3 mm, a short axis of 4.8 mm, and an equi-volume diameter of 16.5 mm.
- Group (5): Large particles with a long axis of 18.5 mm, a short axis of 3.7 mm, and an equi-volume diameter of 7.2 mm.
- Group (16): The most representative biomass particle size group for this boiler, with dimensions of 20 mm (long axis), 1.5 mm (short axis), and 3.5 mm (equi-volume diameter). The equi-volume diameter of 3.5 mm is comparable to the maximum particle size used in modern suspension-firing boilers.
- Group (18): Small particles, measuring 4.5 mm (long axis), 0.53 mm (short axis), and 1 mm (equi-volume diameter). The equi-volume diameter of 1 mm aligns closely with, and is slightly higher than, the average size of biomass particles used in suspension-firing boilers today.
- Group (20): Second-smallest particles, with dimensions of 1.25 mm (long axis), 0.22 mm (short axis), and 0.45 mm (equi-volume diameter).

The smallest particles (Group (21)) are excluded from Fig. 4 due to their very high spin rates (up to 6,600 rad/s about their minor axes and

71 rad/s about their major axes), which obscure the angular velocity data of larger particles. With dimensions of 0.3 mm (long axis), 0.1 mm (short axis), and 0.165 mm (equi-volume diameter), Group (21) particles are significantly smaller than the average biomass particle sizes used in suspension-firing boilers today. Including them would largely compromise the clarity of the data shown in Fig. 4.

The results in Fig. 4 provide groundbreaking insights into the rotational behavior of biomass particles under real operational conditions. First, biomass particles predominantly rotate around their minor axes (x' or y' axis), with angular velocities about these being 1–2 orders of magnitude higher than those about their major axes (z' axis). This distinction is clearly illustrated in Fig. 4(a) and (b) compared to Fig. 4(c). Second, particle rotation significantly intensifies as particle size decreases. This is primarily because smaller particles have lower moments of inertia about their axes, making them more responsive to local fluid vorticity, flow separation and external forces. As a result, smaller particles rotate more easily and achieve higher angular velocities when subjected to flow-induced forces, especially in high-vorticity regions of turbulent flows. Notably, this phenomenon, i.e., lower moments of inertia enabling smaller particles to better respond to local variations in fluid vorticity, is a behavior analogous to their translational motion dynamics. With shorter particle momentum response times (lower Stokes numbers), smaller particles can more readily follow the local fluid flow structure. In contrast, larger particles, characterized by higher Stokes numbers, are less affected by the surrounding fluid flow and are less responsive to these variations. In addition, smaller particles experience stronger effects from viscous damping and flow-separation damping in turbulent flows, further intensifying their rotational motion. For biomass particles with equi-volume diameters of 16.5 mm (Group 0), 7.2 mm (Group (5)), 3.5 mm (Group (16)), 1 mm (Group (18)), 450 μm (Group (20)), and 165 μm (Group (21)), excluded from Fig. 4, the peak angular velocities about their minor axes reach up to 4, 38, 64, 267, 890, and 6,600 rad/s, respectively. In contrast, their angular velocities about the major axes are considerably lower (by 1–2 orders of magnitude), at approximately 0.03, 0.1, 3.6, 9.3, 23, and 71 rad/s, respectively.

Compared to conventional particle-tracking models, which focus solely on particle translation and neglect rotation, the novel model provides unprecedented insights into particle rotational behaviors, which plays a critical role in particle dynamics, mixing, and reactions. Moreover, it greatly improves simulation accuracy without noticeably compromising overall simulation efficiency.

In a CFD study on optimizing a woodchip and coal co-firing retrofit for a power utility (Gao et al., 2016), the rotation of woodchip particles about their centers of mass was not solved. Instead, a fixed 45° angle between the particle axis and the drag force was assumed when calculating the projected particle area normal to the drag force direction, based on the drag coefficient proposed by Ganser (1993). However, considering the incidence angles in Fig. 4(d), an average angle of 90° between the particle major axis and the drag force would be a more reasonable assumption. This adjustment would lead to a more physically realistic representation of woodchip particle motion and conversion, ultimately improving the reliability of the co-firing retrofit optimization.

4.2. Impact on particle dynamics and residence time

Conventional models account only for drag and gravity forces in the equation of particle translational motion (Eq. (1)). In these models, drag coefficients depend solely on the particle Reynolds number (as in spherical drag laws, Eq. (2)) or on both the particle Reynolds number and shape factor (as in non-spherical particle drag laws, Eq. (3)).

In contrast, the novel model incorporates all key forces in the equation of particle translational motion (Eq. (5)). Crucially, the drag and lift coefficients in this model are derived from thousands of particle-resolved direct numerical simulations across a broad range of flow and particle conditions characterized by particle Reynolds number, aspect

(a) Trajectories of all 1,848 particle streams released from the inlet's center core, colored by particle residence time (two identical pairs of dashed boxes only to facilitate comparison of lateral dispersion)

(b) Drag coefficients of five particle size groups released from the same location under identical conditions

Fig. 5. (a) Trajectories of all particle streams, (b) Drag coefficients of representative particle size groups.

ratio, and incidence angle. This ensures high accuracy and broad applicability of the drag and lift coefficients employed.

As a result of these advancements, the novel model predicts different particle trajectories and residence times. Qualitatively, it exhibits greater lateral dispersion of biomass particles in the co-fired burner chamber due to lift forces, asymmetric drag forces, and particle rotation. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 5(a), where two identical pairs of dashed boxes are placed at the same chamber location to facilitate comparison of lateral dispersion of particles. In Case 1 (conventional spherical drag law for equi-volume spheres), all the particle streams are well confined within the 3-meter-in-diameter cylindrical chamber throughout their journey, with no contact with the lateral wall at all. In contrast, in Case 2 (non-spherical drag law for equi-volume spheres) and Case 3 (novel closed model for prolate ellipsoids), a small fraction of particle streams hit the bottom wall near the outlet.

Quantitatively, the average residence times of biomass particles in the 10-meter-long burner chamber are: 0.5852 s for Case 1, 0.6578 s for Case 2, and 0.6938 s for Case 3. Compared to the commonly used spherical drag law, the non-spherical drag law increases particle residence time by 12.4 %, while the novel model extends it by 18.6 %. However, this contradicts the findings of Liu and Shen (2018) and Guo et al. (2020), who reported shorter particle residence times for non-spherical particle models in combustion chambers compared to conventional spherical particle models.

Fig. 5(b) presents the drag coefficients of five representative particle size groups released from the same location under identical conditions. The drag coefficients exhibit significant variation over time due to substantial differences in particle Reynolds numbers (or relative velocity

between gas and particle) and particle orientations (or incidence angles) at various points along the particle trajectory, as evidenced by Eq. (12). Two key issues should be highlighted. First, the drag coefficient is defined based on the diameter of an equi-volume spherical particle. The drag force (as well as lift and torque) is calculated using the surface area of the equi-volume spherical particle, consistent with conventional particle-tracking models, as shown in Eq. (7). Second, the smallest particles (Group (21) are excluded from Fig. 5(b) due to their even higher drag coefficients (up to several hundred), which would obscure the distinctions among larger particles in the plot. The higher drag coefficients (or larger drag force), along with the extra lift force and significant particle rotation, contribute to longer residence times for irregular biomass particles (Case 3), compared to spherical particles regardless of whether a spherical or non-spherical drag law is used (Case 1 or Case 2). Accurately predicting residence time is crucial for biomass co-firing simulations, as it largely affects overall combustion performance and gaseous trace pollutant emissions (Zhou et al., 2016).

4.3. Impact on reactions and burnout

The particle concentration contour provides an indication of particle trajectories and fates. Even within the short residence time in this 10-meter-long co-fired burner chamber, the different computational cases exhibit remarkably distinct particle concentration profiles and trajectories. Due to longer residence times and better mixing, the novel model predicts faster particle mass loss (volatile release), as evidenced by the quicker decay in particle concentrations in Fig. 6(a) and the earlier release of biomass volatiles in Fig. 6(b). Additionally, the thicker zone of

Fig. 6. Mixing and reaction profiles at the vertical mid-plane for the three computational cases.

high volatile mass fractions in Fig. 6(b) suggests that the novel model predicts greater lateral dispersion of biomass particles.

Fig. 6(c) shows the O_2 mass fraction along the co-fired burner for the three computational cases. The significant release of volatiles from biomass particles rapidly depletes O_2 , leaving insufficient oxygen for effective char burnout. This highlights the potential for optimizing the air supply to ensure adequate and timely oxygen availability for char combustion. In addition to the large particle sizes and short residence times, the improper air supply contributes to the consistently low char burnout observed in all three cases. Complete burnout of even smaller biomass particles – ranging from a few hundred micrometers to a few millimeters – typically requires residence times of several seconds in the combustion zone (Momeni et al., 2013; Yin, 2020), far longer than those experienced by the much bigger particles in this co-fired burner chamber.

Fig. 6(d) presents the temperature profiles for the three cases. Near the outer radius, the temperatures are similar due to the influence of natural gas combustion, as indicated by the co-fired burner structure in Fig. 2(b). However, closer to the centerline and further downstream, more pronounced temperature differences emerge, reflecting variations in biomass particle dynamics and conversion behaviors predicted by the respective particle-tracking models.

It is essential to emphasize that the three computational cases differ only in their particle-tracking models, while all other parameters, conditions and considerations remain identical. For instance, in the conventional model using either the spherical (Case 1) or non-spherical drag law (Case 2), particle shape factors (Θ), defined as the ratio of the surface area of an equi-volume sphere (A_s) to the actual surface area of an irregular biomass particle (A_s), $\Theta = \frac{A_s}{A_s}$, are incorporated into the particle-gas heat and mass exchange processes and the enhanced char

combustion model. This approach is identical to that used in the novel model (Case 3). In all the three cases, the shape factor Θ is applied to each particle group to modify the particle specific heat c_p to assure a consistent particle heating rate and to adjust the binary diffusivity $D_{i,m}$ to assure the same particle mass loss rate during char oxidation.

$$m_p c_p \frac{dT_p}{dt} = A_p \left[h(T_\infty - T_p) + \varepsilon_p \sigma (\theta_R^4 - T_p^4) \right] \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{dm_p}{dt} = -4\pi d_p D_{i,m} \frac{Y_{ox} T_\infty \rho}{S_b (T_p + T_\infty)} \quad (21)$$

where T_p , A_p , T_∞ , ε_p , σ , θ_R , d_p , Y_{ox} , ρ , and S_b represent particle temperature, surface area of equi-volume spherical particle, local gas temperature, particle emissivity, Stefan-Boltzmann constant, local radiation temperature, diameter of equi-volume spherical particle, local mass fraction of oxygen, local gas density, and stoichiometry in char surface oxidation, respectively. In all the three cases, c_p in Eq. (20) is adjusted to $\frac{c_p}{\Theta}$, and $D_{i,m}$ in Eq. (21) is adjusted to $\phi_{en} D_{i,m} = D_{i,m} \frac{0.3\Theta + 0.7}{\Theta}$ for all particle groups, based on their shape factors. If Θ were not considered in Case 1 or Case 2, the heat and mass exchange rates would decrease by a factor of $1/\Theta$, as equi-volume spheres have the smallest surface area compared to irregular particles. The average particle shape factor for the biomass particles co-fired in this boiler is $\Theta = 0.5208$, meaning that particles in Case 1 or Case 2 would heat up at only half the rate of those in Case 3. A similar effect will be observed during char surface oxidation, where the char oxidation rate is significantly lower if the enhancement factor ϕ_{en} is not considered in Case 1 or Case 2. This slower heating and oxidation, combined with shorter residence time and poorer mixing and dispersion, would further delay biomass particle conversion and mass loss via volatile release and char oxidation. Consequently, the differences in

particle behavior and combustion performance become more pronounced. Furthermore, in a full-scale utility boiler, the novel particle-tracking model is expected to show even greater deviations from conventional models, as particle residence times increase from the current 0.6–0.7 s to several seconds within the furnace.

The integration of the novel particle-tracking model into biomass combustion simulations does not noticeably compromise computational efficiency for two key reasons. First, the novel model requires solving only several additional ordinary differential equations, which imposes minimal computational cost. Second, particle tracking is performed at a lower frequency relative to flow calculations. For example, particles are tracked and updated in the Lagrangian framework only once every 25–50 Eulerian flow calculations. As a result, the novel model can seamlessly replace conventional models and serve as the primary tool for particle tracking, even in industrial CFD simulations, delivering more accurate and comprehensive results.

Finally, the framework of the novel model for tracking irregular particles has undergone thorough validation and has proven to be robust. It is capable of handling particles of any size or shape by incorporating corresponding drag, lift and torque coefficients derived from comprehensive PR-DNS. However, when applied to specific scenarios, it is essential to carefully review and assess the accuracy and applicability of various non-spherical particle drag, lift and torque coefficients. Particular attention should be paid to factors such as particle shape and particle-flow conditions in future work. For example, in combustion simulations of chopped straw particles, which are better represented as cylindrical particles with varying aspect ratios, it is essential to incorporate the drag, lift and torque coefficients derived for a wide range of flow conditions and cylindrical particles (Wang et al., 2024c), specifically within the ranges $1 \leq Re_p \leq 4000$, $0^\circ \leq \theta_i \leq 90^\circ$, and $1 \leq \beta \leq 30$. Similarly, in modern biomass combustion, where biomass pellets are milled into flat disk-shaped particles and burned in combustion furnaces, the drag, lift and torque coefficients derived for disk-shaped particles (Wang et al., 2025b) should be integrated. These coefficients cover a wide flow and particle conditions, $1 \leq Re_p \leq 2000$, $0^\circ \leq \theta_i \leq 90^\circ$, and $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a novel closed model for tracking irregular particles in dilute multiphase flows, accurately resolving their coupled translational and rotational dynamics. The model integrates drag, lift, and torque coefficients derived from thousands of particle-resolved simulations across diverse flow and particle conditions, coupled with an analytical discretization scheme to update particle velocities and orientations. This ensures exceptional accuracy, numerical robustness and broad applicability. The model's capabilities are demonstrated through CFD simulations of a biomass co-fired burner chamber, offering groundbreaking insights into the rotational behavior of biomass particles under real-world firing conditions. It significantly improves simulation outcomes, such as extended particle residence times, enhanced mixing, stronger lateral particle dispersion, and intensified phase interactions. Despite its advanced formulation, the model remains computationally efficient, making it a practical tool for engineering applications. Its ability to accurately capture intricate particle-flow interactions positions it as a valuable asset for optimizing multiphase flow reactors.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Chungun Yin reports financial support was provided by Europe Horizons. Chungun Yin reports a relationship with Horizon Europe that includes: funding grants. If there are other authors, they declare that they

have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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